
Traditional and Modern Methods of Crime Prevention and Control in Nigeria: The Need for Integration

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Abstract

Despite the global acceptance of modern methods of crime prevention and control, traditional systems remain influential in many African communities. This persistence stems from the limitations of modern security institutions in addressing crime comprehensively. This paper argues for the integration of traditional and modern methods of crime prevention and control in Nigeria. Drawing from secondary data sourced from journals and relevant publications, the study employed content analysis to examine the role of both approaches. Findings reveal that traditional institutions such as vigilante groups, age-grade associations, and cultural sanctions remain effective at community levels. The study concludes that integrating traditional and modern methods will strengthen Nigeria's crime-fighting capacity. Policy recommendations are provided for harmonizing these systems.

Keywords: Crime prevention, Crime control, Traditional method, Modern method, Law enforcement, Criminal justice system, Indigenous crime control

Introduction

A safe and secure environment remains fundamental to the socio-economic and political development of any nation. However, Nigeria has continued to grapple with pervasive insecurity manifesting in terrorism, banditry, kidnapping, armed robbery, electoral violence, and farmer/herder conflicts (Adebayo, 2021; Okolie & Ordu, 2023). Despite huge investments in modern security agencies such as the Nigeria Police Force, the military, and paramilitary institutions, insecurity persists, undermining human security and sustainable development (Oyeleke, 2022). This reflects the inadequacy of conventional policing mechanisms, which are often plagued by poor funding, corruption, lack of trust, and weak community relations (Aborisade & Fayemi, 2020).

The United Nations (1990) emphasized that crime prevention strategies must go beyond law enforcement to include developmental and community-based approaches. In this regard, community participation and partnership policing have gained attention globally (Rosenbaum et al., 2021; Shah, 2021). Experiences from the United States, the United Kingdom, and South Asia show that collaboration between law enforcement agencies and local communities enhances intelligence gathering, trust, and effective policing outcomes (Johnson, 2020; Shah, 2021).

In Nigeria, the failure of modern policing to adequately manage insecurity has revived reliance on traditional security structures such as vigilante groups, hunters' associations, age-grade organizations, and community militias (Aina & Odiji, 2019; Olawale, 2024). These groups leverage local knowledge, cultural legitimacy, and community trust to address insecurity, especially in rural areas where state security presence is limited (Okunade, 2021). Although traditional approaches are sometimes criticized for human rights abuses, evidence suggests that integrating them with modern crime prevention frameworks could enhance national security architecture (Aborisade & Fayemi, 2020; Ogbozor, 2016).

This paper therefore examines the imperative of integrating traditional and modern methods of crime prevention and control as a holistic strategy for addressing Nigeria complex insecurity.

Statement of the Problem

Crime in Nigeria has become increasingly complex due to urbanization, technology, and globalization. Modern security agencies alone have proven inadequate in addressing these challenges (Ogbozor, 2016; Oyeleke, 2022). Communities often resort to self-help through vigilante groups, yet these efforts remain uncoordinated with state agencies and sometimes result in human rights violations (Olawale, 2024). Thus, there is a pressing need to synergize traditional and modern security mechanisms to reduce insecurity while safeguarding human rights and social justice (Okolie & Ordu, 2023).

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine traditional methods of crime prevention and control in Nigeria.
2. To analyze modern approaches to crime prevention and control.
3. To assess the effectiveness and challenges of both systems.
4. To argue for the integration of traditional and modern methods in Nigeria's security architecture.

Theoretical Framework

Partnership Theory of Crime Prevention

This theory is traced to the work of Dennis P. Rosenbaum's (2003) "multi-agency anti – crime partnership theory". The theory posits that, the agencies of the criminal justice system alone cannot solve the complex and myriad problems of crime, insecurity and disorder. It involves a collaborative and cooperative relationship between partners or organization to achieving common goals especially of crime control and prevention and security in a society. The theory therefore advocate for the creation of "partnership" i.e a group of organization and inter –organizational corporations synergizing distinctive but complementary skills & resources that can produce coordinating and targeted responses to crime prevention (Rosembaum et al., 2021).

Theory of Community Participation

The theory posits that, when the people of a community are involved and are carried along in solving their own problem, it produces quick and enduring result to solving the social problem when the people are directly involved and participate in solving their problems, it gives them a sense of belongingness control over their own affairs and decisions, it afford the privilege of redistributing power and thus ensure equal and unanimous participation of all in the community (Arnstein, 1969). Participation brings about collective and consensus decision making belongingness (Kreuter; Lezin & Young, 2000; Bracht & Tsouros, 1990). Community participation enhances community collectivism, general participation of the people of a society. Recent studies affirm that community participation enhances intelligence gathering and strengthens resilience against insecurity (Johnson, 2020; Okunade, 2021).

In essence, "partnership policing and community participation" in crime control and prevention are essential elements of "community policing strategies" (Miller & Hess, 2002). The appositeness of these theoretical orientations is hinged on the understanding that, the criminal justice system (CJS) alone cannot singly solve the complex problem of crime, especially in a modernising and technologically advancing society. No agency, organization or institution can singly solve the complexity of crime. Therefore, it is compellingly circumstantial for a participation, involvement and partnership between the modern security agencies (i.e. criminal justice system) and the various traditional security agencies in managing and abating crime and insecurity to its barest minimum. This is hinged on the understanding that; the locale of a community are stakeholders in their communities. They do not only understand the terrain of their neighbourhoods and environment better, but also have the stake of upholding, promoting and protecting the values, security and safety of their community. Consequently, this explains the increasing agitation for state police, community policing system, police-community relations, various states' security outfits and various informal policing system in Nigeria.

Traditional Methods of Crime Prevention and Control

To appreciate the effectiveness of traditional methods of Crime prevention and control, it is pertinent to identify the major categories of crime in traditional society. These according to Igbo (1999) are; Crime against Individuals, Crime against the community, and Crime against the spiritual world. Traditional systems are culturally embedded and historically effective in promoting conformity. These include: Vigilante groups and hunters' associations: Provide local security and assist state agencies in combating banditry and insurgency (Aina & Odiji,

2019; Ocheja & Aina, 2020). Age-grade organizations: Function as disciplinary and community development bodies (Talbot, 1999; Omagu, 1979). It performed both social and political functions; and inculcate healthy ideas and objectives in their members and further act as a disciplinary body for erring members. This was done by subjecting such members who violate the societal (social) norms to sanctions and punishment. Talboth (1999) buttresses this assertion and noted that age-grades are very essential in the chain of government and without them the administrative functions could hardly be carried out. Specifically, age-grades look after road maintenance and other developmental projects, others act as police in the community.

Religion is an important tool for the moral well-being of the community has been advanced in many forms. One of such is that, religion is useful as a cohesive factor, holding the society and its morality together in such a way that whoever attacks the society's religion is deemed to have attacked the society. Religion has also been seen as a source of strength and consolation, and essential for moral education, moral endeavour and moral achievement (Akiba, 2012). Given that African societies are relatively undifferentiated and homogenous and religiously disposed, meaning that religion governs our lineage and family relationship; religion means collectivity, and forms the basis of social control (Akiba, 2012). It was the religious ties that created propitious leverage for strong community ties and less crime in African traditional societies. In relation to criminal behaviour, religion has sought to solve these problems, because it legitimizes our values and provides reasons why certain values should be preferred to others (Ayuk, 2016).

Cultural sanctions: Oath-taking, curses, ridicule, and gossip serve as moral regulators. According to Oba (2015) argued that the use of curses to compel people to respect their taboos and laws served as prevention and control. Curses were generally feared because of the belief that defaulters would be inflicted with protracted sickness, sudden death or other calamities. However, irrespective of the means used, certain agents and means of prevention and control have come to be commonly identified by this direction.

Recent evidence shows vigilante groups who act as police in the various communities they subsist. They are watchmen, guards, members of the communities are organized to suppress and punish crime summarily as when the process of law appears inadequate as the case with Nigeria. Civilian Joint Task Forces (CJTF) play critical roles in complementing the military against Boko Haram in the Northeast (Olawale, 2024).

Modern Methods of Crime Prevention and Control

According to Okunola (2015) the modern methods of Crime prevention and control are, however, closely related and their elements overlap. Crime prevention involves the community, government as well as individuals; crime control involves the whole of the criminal justice system, that is, the police, courts and prison.

The major tasks of **the Police** include selectively enforcing the law, protecting the public, arresting suspected law violators, and preventing crime. After police investigation of the offender, the offender is charge to court for further interpretation of the law.

The Court; courts are run by judges whose role is to make sure the law is followed and oversee what happens in court. They decide whether to release offender before the trial. Judge accept or reject plea agreements, oversee trials, and sentence convicted offenders.

The Correctional Services: Correction officers supervise convicted offenders when they are in jail or in community probation or parole. In some communities, Correction officers prepare pre-sentencing reports with extensive background information about the offender to help judges decide sentences. The job of correction officers is to make sure the facilities that hold offenders are secure and safe. They oversee the day to day custody of inmates. They also oversee the release process for inmates and sometimes notify victims of changes in the offender's status. The establishment of other agencies like State Security Services (SSS), Independent Corrupt Practices and other related Offences Commission (ICPC), and the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) is a laudable effort towards crime prevention and control, their narrow focus and few personnel inhibits it from functioning in a broad day to day manner like the police. Some of them apart from the State Security Service that is consigned to the gathering of intelligence reports don't exist even at the State and Local Government levels.

They leaves the day to day policing of the entire country more at the door-step of the police. The capacity of the police and other agencies in Nigeria to effectively prevent and control crime has often been called to question. As a matter of fact, many have lost faith in the security agencies going by the incessant increase in the crime rate. According to Okunola (2015), crime prevention basically involves the distribution of mechanisms, which cause events. In other words, the central question to crime prevention is how to disrupt the causes of crime.

Crime prevention through Social Development

According to Agbola (1997:31) this is a relatively new approach to crime prevention, pioneered by sociologists and victimologists. This approach relies on the premise that there is a well-established body of research that can identify factors contributory to crime. It is the effects of these contributing factors that crime prevention through social Development strives to alleviate. According to Agbola, the efforts to this approach includes initiatives to reduce poverty and to increase the availability of proper housing, employment, education, and adequate recreational facilities.

The Proponent of this approach contend that, there is a group of people in the society who bear the brunt of social injustice. They are the downtrodden and poverty vulnerable groups. Having come to the end of their wits according to this perspective, members of these disadvantaged groups resort to crime in order to correct societal imbalances. From the perspective of this strategy, mere proscription of these conducts may not provide the expected solution. It appear that the only measure that can reasonably prevent or at least reduce the valve of crime in Nigeria, is the initiation and enforcement of flawless social policies that would address the intricate problems of; Lack of educational opportunities unemployment, social injustice, poverty and social inequality. (Agbola, 1997; Aborisade&Fayemi, 2020).

Crime Prevention through Environmental Design

Despite the appeal of the social development approach discussed above, the current strategy for crime prevention which has been receiving attention from various authors according to Agbola, (CPTED). This approach is basically concerned with the manipulation of the physical environment in order to deter crime. It is not intended to create an impregnable fortress, but merely to make penetration more difficult and time consuming.

Furthermore, this approach seeks to project the notion that the physical environment and criminal behaviour are related in an architectural context. This approach further subscribes to

the view that territorial ownership, natural surveillance, image and milieu and functional location are measures which can be used to mitigate residential crime in urban areas. The elements of (CPTED) currently advocated by other protagonists of this approach such as Mukoro (1986) include the following strategies; territorial behaviour, surveillance, barriers, lighting, landscaping and scar tactics. (Mukoro, 1986; Oyeleke, 2022). Despite these measures, modern approaches face limitations such as corruption, weak funding, and poor community trust (Aborisade & Fayemi, 2020).

Assessment of Effectiveness

Security experts have acknowledged that any comprehensive strategy to reduce crime must not only include the contributions of the police and the criminal justice system but also a holistic approach incorporating environmental, social, economic and educational factors which influence the likelihood of crime. The overwhelmingly increasing and unabated trends of insecurity, and the apparent inability and inadequacy of the modern method security agencies to curb the situation alone have propelled the need to integrate the traditional and modern method of crime prevention and control in addressing the menace of crime and insecurity (Fulton & Nickels, 2017). Comparative advantage and experiences have proven that this integration approach is most effective to achieving positive results and creating safer environment. In United state of America, police officers partner with citizens in the neighbourhood, business environment, private policing agents and other law enforcement agencies to achieve effective policing. Other countries that have been involved in this public-policing partnership are, Britain, Pakistan, etc. This has proven to be effective against the rising tide of crime (Johnson, 2020; Shah, 2021).

In 2015 Local Vigilante in Kwara State were invited by the Kogi State Government in conjunction with vigilante and police to combat the terror of armed robbery, Kidnapping and Banditry between kabba-obajana Lokoja road (Ocheja & Aina, 2020). The operation was successfully carried out, and a lot of the criminals were arrested, some were eliminated. Vigilante and Civilian JTF have proven to be veritable collaborators with the military and other security agencies in the fight against insurgency in the Northeast Nigeria (Aina & Odiji 2019), kidnapping, armed robbery, banditry etc. in other part of the country, they have better understanding of their communities and operational terrain of insurgency and terrorist. They have aided the military and other security agents in identifying structures and modus operandi of the insurgent through local intelligence and reconnaissance. They have been instrumental in the arrests of high profiles Boko Haram suspects and rescuing some of their abductors (ETTis, 2012) Traditional methods of crime prevention and control are effective in adjudicating land disputes (land grabbing), rape and theft, armed robbery, kidnapping among other cases, for example the issues of rape and theft were resolved through Ridicule and Gossips with regard to this, deviation from expected norms and values consequently attracted unfavourable reactions from friends and mostly in the forms of ridicules and gossips which served as powerful instruments of crime prevention and control (Ocheja & Aina 2020). However, when a girl got pregnant before marriage for instance, becomes automatically an object of ridicule and gossip. With this, her name often becomes the latest music in the community and readily amplified at her appearance in any public gathering. The same treatment is often applied to thieves and other deviants. Since most individuals inherently don't want to be disgraced publicly, they try to avoid deviant conducts/behaviours.

Challenges of Integration

There is constitutional challenges, recently the Attorney General of the Federation and Minister of Justice declared Amotekun a security agency in South West illegal because, no legal backing for the formation (Okolie & Ordu, 2023)

Secondly, there is role conflict, when there are incompatible demands place upon a person relating to their job or positions, conflicts among the role begins because of the human desire to reach success, and because of the pressure put on an individual by two imposing and incompatible demands competing against each other., the police are not happy for fear of been taking over their own responsibility from them.

Funding and training gap for local security actors: Who train the traditional vigilante, at what level, which methods and what type of weapon to use at what capacity are the challenges of integrating traditional and modern methods of crime prevention and control, lack of cooperation between the traditional and modern pattern of crime prevention and control and finally (Alemika & Chukwuma, 2003)

Human rights concerns, including extrajudicial killings (Olawale, 2024).

Conclusion

There is an overwhelmingly increasing and unabated trend of crime and insecurity in Nigeria. The apparent inability and inadequacy of the modern security agencies alone to curb the situation have propelled the establishment of various traditional or informal security agencies and operators. Thus, reinforcing the collaboration of modern – traditional security agencies in addressing the menace of crime and insecurity in Nigeria. The ‘collaborative policing approach’ has proven to be most effective in the fight against crime and insecurity, and ensuring a safe environment. Some of the collaborating traditional or informal security operators in Nigeria are the vigilante, neighbourhood watch, hunters, civilian-JTF, Amotekun, Forest Guards, Private Security Companies, etc.

Furthermore, the traditional security operators have better understanding of their communities, operational terrain of insurgents and terrorists. They are familiar with the itinerants and routes of the forest and can easily identify and trace human foot from that of animals. They possess and apply their local and traditional intelligence and skills. They provide policing services to their local communities, and assist the military and the police in identifying, arresting and spying suspects. They have been instrumental in the arrest of high profile suspected insurgents and kidnappers and rescue of their hostages. They are poised to be proactive and quick response to crime and insecurity in their communities, because of their proximity to the people and resident within the community. Notwithstanding their highhandedness and extrajudicial activities, yet their significance and effectiveness in the fight against insecurity, terrorism and insurgency in the country cannot be underestimated.

Thus, “partnership or collaborative policing strategies” have proven to be significant and effective in crime prevention and control in Nigeria. There is no universal collaborating policing strategy, thus, each country and localities adopt the various partnerships policing techniques to suit their crime specific needs. This principle of “localisation” i.e. seeking local solutions to local issues is a sine qua non for the development of partnership policing in Nigeria, with numerous crimes and insecurity challenges spread across all states and geo-political zones

Policy Recommendations

1. Recognize and formalize traditional security structures within Nigeria's security architecture.
2. Provide regular training and capacity-building for vigilante groups.
3. Institutionalize police–community partnerships for intelligence sharing.
4. Constitutionally empower states and local governments to fund and regulate local security outfits.
5. Strengthen family and social welfare systems to address root causes of crime.

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